

Modelling a Power Electronic Converter System for Stand-alone Variable Speed Diesel Gen-Set

R. Luís* rluis@deea.isel.ipl.pt
J.C. Quadrado* jcquadrado@deea.isel.ipl.pt

* Instituto Superior de Engenharia de Lisboa
R. Conselheiro Emídio Navarro, 1959-007 Lisboa, Portugal

S. Ferreira Pinto** pcsoniafp@alfa.ist.utl.pt
J. Fernando Silva** fernandos@alfa.ist.utl.pt

** Instituto Superior Técnico, CIEEE, DEEC, AC Energia
Av. Rovisco Pais, 1049-001 Lisboa, Portugal

Abstract — The purpose of this paper is the modelling and simulation a power electronic converter system for a stand-alone variable speed diesel gen-set. The main goal to use a power electronic converter system is due to electrical energy processing of the variable speed permanent magnet generator to a constant frequency and constant rms voltage output. The variable speed gen-set should be able to supply both linear/non-linear and balanced/unbalanced loads at constant voltage and frequency at optimum engine fuel consumption.

Keywords - Variable speed generators; diesel engine; permanent-magnet generator; back-to-back power electronic converter; optimum engine fuel trajectory; unbalanced loads.

I. INTRODUCTION

The power generation systems in isolated electric grid aim to serve the energy demands of a place, by producing energy near the point of use. These systems allow the generation of electricity in remote areas, which are located away from the centralized systems power generation, often make it economically unfeasible to expand a network of distribution of electricity to those places.

The use of a diesel generator set (gen-set) consisting of an internal combustion engine coupled to an electric generator, is one possible solutions and commonly used for the electrification of remote locations.

The stand-alone standard gen-set uses a three-phase brushless self-excited synchronous generator driven by a diesel combustion engine at constant rotational speed. The three-phase output voltages are constant in their amplitude and frequency due the control loops of the automatic voltage regulator and the engine speed governor, respectively.

The main problem of usual gen-set solution is related to their use in load transients. A gen-set operates with the best fuel consumption, when used near its rated power. Significant changes in demand result in poor performance in the diesel engine efficiency, higher maintenance costs and less environmental protection.

The global objectives in this work, which begins with a numeric simulation study, is accomplish: increase the system efficiency, lower fuel consumptions, reduce the maintenance costs and achieve better environmental protection. The system should be controlled in independently of the load, so that optimal engine operation is achieved for a wide range of the load power demands, [1]-[2].

To implement these targets, reducing the gen-sets operational costs, the conceptual solution is based on diesel

engine operating under variable speed and the use an AC/AC power electronic converter to process the energy produced by the electric generator, to be applied to the load, [3]-[4].

The AC/AC power electronic converters could have also an extra energy stored system connected to DC-bus, to enhance the output power quality and/or to increase the output transient response, [5].

This work is focused in variable speed gen-set using permanent-magnet synchronous generator (PMSG) and an AC/AC power electronic converter with voltage DC-link capacitor. Other solutions applied to variable speed gen-sets could be found in technical publications, such as the doubly-fed induction generator, [6]-[7], and the PMSG with direct matrix power electronic converters, [8]-[9].

This paper is organized as following: the next section a brief state of the art about adjustable speed gen-sets with PMSG and AC/AC power electronic converter with voltage DC-link capacitor is presented. The following two sections a variable speed gen-set model and their numerical simulations results are presented and discussed. The paper closes with the conclusions and future work on this subject.

II. PM GENERATOR AND AC/AC CONVERTER

During the last decade, two main topologies solutions for variable speed gen-sets using AC/AC converter with DC-link capacitor were proposed and implemented:

- using PMSG with diode rectifier and PWM inverter;
- using PMSG with back-to-back power electronic converter connected to the load.

A. PMSG and Diode rectifier + PWM inverter solution

This adjustable speed generating system, Fig. 1, has the main blocks: diesel engine as a prime mover; PMSG and the AC/AC power electronic converter.

Fig. 1 – Variable speed gen-set with AC/AC converter.

The AC/AC converter has a three-phase bridge diode rectifier, a boost converter, DC-link capacitor and a three-phase inverter.

The diode rectifier makes the first stage of the AC/AC power conversion. The boost converter is a DC-DC converter applied to stabilize the DC-bus voltage and to control the generator rectified current. The inverter is controlled to produce three-phase voltages with the desired amplitude and frequency, [10]-[12]. The neutral wire output connection in order to handle the neutral current caused by unbalanced load is also possible, [13]-[14].

A three-phase LC filter reduces the output waveform harmonic distortion.

B. PMSG and back-to-back converter solution

The Fig. 2 presents the back-to-back power electronic converter solution.

Fig. 2 – Variable speed gen-set with back-to-back converter.

The main difference of this variable speed gen-set solution compared with previous is that this AC/AC converter has an active front-end rectifier.

With the active rectifier the DC-bus voltage can be directly controlled and the boost converter of the previous solution is not necessary, [15]. On other hand, the low harmonics imposed by the diode rectifier degrade the generator control and reduce its efficiency.

III. VARIABLE SPEED GEN-SET MODEL

The power electronic converter system for stand-alone variable speed gen-set that is under scope of this paper is presented in Fig.3.

This presented solution is a back-to-back power electronic converter type. The gen-set has the diesel engine as the prime mover and a variable speed PMSG.

The following sections present the simulation model of this adjustable speed gen-set system.

A. Diesel engine modelling and speed control

The energy conversion process of the diesel engines involves a high mathematical and physical complexity, [16]. The torque developed in a diesel engine is a nonlinear function of many variables, such as fuel mass in cylinder, air/fuel ratio, engine speed, ignition or injection timing, exhaust-gas recirculation rate, etc. To predict developed engine torque, considering all variables that involve this energy conversion process, detailed thermodynamic simulations are required, [17].

In this research study, the diesel engine model is based on its performance map. This approach provides a measure of how efficiently an engine is using the fuel supplied to produce mechanical power. The performance map is a graphic representation that contains the information, at steady-state operation, of the diesel engine fuel consumption, given the load and speed.

From [18], the diesel engine performance map presented in Fig. 4 was adopted for this numerical simulation work.

The main data of the diesel engine are 37kW as maximum power at 5000rpm and 85Nm as maximum torque at 3000rpm.

Fig. 4 – Diesel engine performance map.

In Fig. 4 the gradient colour contour lines represents the specific fuel consumption in g/kWh units; the deep blue line represents the maximum torque at given speed; the black curve lines the engine mechanical power output and the red line across the specific fuel consumption contour lines represents the optimum fuel consumption trajectory. This trajectory is used as the reference for the variable speed gen-set operation.

Due the highly non-linear behaviour of diesel engines, for the study of dynamics of complete system, a simplified diesel engine model can be used in numerical simulation. Thus, a 1st order model for the engine actuator is considered, where its time delay constant represents the fuel valve dynamics. The diesel engine combustion process is modelling using also a 1st order model, where its time delay constant represents the dynamics of developed torque, T_{eng} .

The diesel engine model and its speed governor control are shown in Fig. 5.

Fig. 5 – Diesel engine model and speed governor control.

The diesel engine speed is regulated by using a PI controller. To minimize the engine fuel consumption, a power-speed look-up table with the optimum fuel trajectory curve is implemented. The input to the look-up table is the required mechanical power, P_{ref} , and the output the speed reference that minimizes the fuel consumption, ω_{ref} .

Fig.3. Variable Speed gen-set: simplified system configuration.

B. PMSG modelling and generator torque control

The PM generator electromagnetic model can be written in a compacted form, (1), [19].

$$[u_{abc}] = [R_s][i_{abc}] + [L_{abc}] \cdot \frac{d}{dt}[i_{abc}] + \frac{d\theta}{dt} \frac{d}{d\theta} [\Psi_{abc}] \quad (1)$$

In (1) $[u_{abc}]$ is the matrix voltages of the PMSG; $[R_s]$, is the resistances matrix of the stator windings; $[i_{abc}]$, is the stator windings currents matrix; $[L_{abc}]$, is the self-induction and mutual induction coefficients matrix; $[\Psi_{abc}]$, represents the linkage fluxes matrix established by permanent magnets in stator windings and t is the electrical angle related to the angular rotor position.

The generator electromagnetic torque, T_{gen} , can be obtained from magnetic coenergy derivative, W_{cm} , in order to the position coordinate, (2), [20].

$$T_{gen} = \frac{\partial W_{cm}}{\partial \theta} = [i_{abc}]^T \frac{d}{d\theta} [\Psi_{abc}] \quad (2)$$

The mechanic equation is given by the second Newton's equation, (3).

$$T_{eng} - T_{gen} = J \frac{d\omega}{dt} + K_d \omega \quad (3)$$

In (3), J represents the inertia moment gen-set shaft; K_d represents the viscous attrition coefficient and ω , the mechanic rotational speed.

The equations (1)-(3) describe the PMSG model in abc coordinates.

For optimum fuel consumption PMSG torque control is required. Using the Park's transformation to previous PMSG model, the electromagnetic torque equation, is obtained in dq referential quantities and can be given from (4), [20].

$$T_{gen} = \frac{3}{2} p i_q [\Psi_m + (L_d - L_q) i_d] \quad (4)$$

Here in (4), p is the number of pole pairs; Ψ_m , the flux established by permanent magnets; L_d and L_q are the inductances in d and q axes, respectively.

For a non-salient-pole machine the stator inductances, L_d and L_q , are approximately equal. This means that the

direct-axis current, i_d does not contribute to the generator electromagnetic torque, T_{gen} . For the generator torque control the concept is to keep i_{dref} null, in order to obtain maximum torque with minimum current, (5).

$$T_{gen} = K_m i_q \quad (5)$$

In (5), K_m represents the PMSG torque constant.

The Fig. 6 shows the block diagram of PMSG model and the generator torque control scheme. From actual rotational speed, ω a look-up table with the optimum fuel trajectory curve, gives the generator torque reference, T_{ref} , which is proportional to the required current on q axis referential, i_{qref} .

The vectorial currents controller (VCC), controls the PMSG currents according to the necessary torque for optimum fuel consumption.

Fig. 6 - Simplified block diagram of PMSG model and generator torque control.

The Fig. 7 presents the VCC that regulates the stator winding currents in $\alpha\beta$ reference frame, controlling the generator torque, within the small band around reference currents. The PMSG currents are compared with the reference currents and the switching commands, γ_a , γ_b and γ_c , for the active front-end converter, are generated by the voltage vector selection table, [21]-[22].

The VCC uses two hysteric comparators to evaluate the current errors in three discrete values: negative, null and positive. This control strategy is followed by using three

level comparators, which are obtained by the sum of the output of two comparators with two different hysteretic levels, large ($\delta_{L\alpha}$, $\delta_{L\beta}$) and narrow ($\delta_{N\alpha}$, $\delta_{N\beta}$). The outputs current errors and the commutation frequency of the semiconductor devices are dependent of the hysteretic comparator window size. Reduced hysteretic leads to reduce errors in control currents, but increases the semiconductor devices commutation frequency, [21]-[22].

Fig. 7 – Block diagram of the stator PMSG currents vectorial controller.

The command signal, ϕ , uses the previous state of the power converter signal commands to select the appropriate null voltage vector that reduces commutation frequency and the power losses of the semiconductors devices.

C. Three-phase, four-leg inverter and constant voltage and frequency control

The main feature of a three-phase inverter, with an additional neutral connection, is its possibility to deal with unbalanced loads in a stand-alone power supply system. In this type application, this solution avoids the use of the electric transformer Δ/Y_g to access to neutral point, reducing the total gen-set dimensions and cost, [23].

The neutral terminal can be connected to the inverter using two different topologies:

- three-phase four-wire. The neutral point is connected to midpoint of the DC-linked capacitors;
- three-phase four-leg. With an additional inverter leg that permits to modify the neutral voltage.

The first solution turns the three-phase inverter three independent single-phase inverters. The result is the zero-sequence harmonics generated, particularly when the load is unbalanced or non-linear, a high voltage ripple over DC-link capacitors is produced by neutral currents, [24].

The four-leg inverter solution requires two additional power switches, but it offers advantages, such as an increased maximum output voltage value, a reduction of neutral currents and the possibility of neutral point voltage control, [24]. In this study the four-leg inverter is considered. As the three-phase currents are independent, the sigma-delta modulation technique applied to each phase and the neutral is adequate for this numerical simulation purpose to obtain the voltage control, Fig.8, [25].

Fig. 8 – Simplified diagram blocks per phase of the output voltage control.

An output three-phase LC filter is also considered to obtain sinusoidal voltages waveforms.

D. DC-bus voltage controller

The main objective of the system is to produce a constant-voltage, constant-frequency output at optimal fuel consumption. To achieve this goal the inverter should be supplied with enough DC-bus voltage. At variable load gen-set operation, to overcome load changes the DC-bus voltage tends to change too. Despite of the stored energy in DC-link capacitor, the engine dynamics is too low when compared with the engine or power electronic converters dynamics.

Then an outer control loop is made to regulate the DC-bus voltage to a fixed and reasonable value utilizing the inner speed control loop of the diesel engine, Fig. 9.

Fig. 9 – DC-bus voltage control.

In Fig. 9, the DC-bus voltage is regulated by a PI controller. The output is the power mechanical power, P_{ref} , that the adjustable speed gen-set need to adapt to the load power changes.

The reference mechanical power, P_{ref} , acts as the input of the engine speed control loop in order to minimize the fuel consumption.

The dynamics of DC-bus voltage is given in (6).

$$\frac{du_{DC}(t)}{dt} = \frac{i_{DC1}(t) - i_{DC2}(t)}{C} \quad (6)$$

In (6), u_{DC} is the DC-bus voltage, i_{DC1} and i_{DC2} represent the DC-bus currents from the active front-end rectifier and from the four-leg inverter, respectively; C is the capacitance of the DC-link capacitor bank.

Considering ideal the semiconductors devices on active front-end rectifier, the current i_{DC1} , is obtained by (7).

$$i_{DC1} = [\gamma_1 \quad \gamma_2 \quad \gamma_3] [i_a \quad i_b \quad i_c]^T \quad (7)$$

In (7) γ_1 , γ_2 and γ_3 are the each leg command signals of the active front-end rectifier and i_a , i_b , and i_c the three-phase currents of the PMSG stator.

In the same way, the three-phase four leg inverter imposes on DC side the current i_{DC2} , which is derived from (8).

$$i_{DC2} = [\lambda_1 \quad \lambda_2 \quad \lambda_3 \quad \lambda_4] [i_A \quad i_B \quad i_C \quad i_N]^T \quad (8)$$

In (8) λ_1 , λ_2 , λ_3 and λ_4 are the each leg command signals of the three-phase four-leg inverter and i_A , i_B , i_C , and i_N the three-phase and neutral currents of the output load.

IV. SIMULATION RESULTS

The variable speed gen-set model was implemented in Matlab/Simulink[®] environment to obtain the numerical simulation results. To taking account the power electronic devices losses the SimPowerSystems[™] toolbox was used, together with power semiconductor parameters to represent their losses.

The Table 1 gives the general simulation conditions of the system. The gen-set start-up procedure is out of the scope of this simulation analysis.

Table 1 – Simulation conditions of the variable speed gen-set

Output RMS voltages:	230/400V; 50Hz
Power loads tested:	20; 10 kW
unbalanced loads (% load per phase):	L ₁ =130%; L ₂ =60%; L ₃ =110%
Simulation tests:	@ constant speed, 3000rpm @ variable speed, 1500 to 5000rpm

The Fig. 10 shows the simulation results for the torque and speed gen-set operating points located on performance map at constant speed (green cross markers) and at variable speed (green dot markers). Comparing the operating points with the specific fuel contour curves in both simulation tests, it concludes that the variable speed operating mode can optimize the fuel consumption to a 10kW power load.

Fig. 10 – Torque vs. speed operating points on gen-set performance map (green dots: variable speed; green crosses: gen-set at 3000rpm).

The Fig. 11 presents the simulation results for the torque and speed inner control loops of the PMSG and diesel engine, respectively.

The Fig. 12 and Fig. 13 show the voltages and currents of the PMSG and of the unbalanced load, respectively.

The analysis of the Figs. 11 to 13 show that the back-to-back converter controls the generator torque with sinusoidal currents and lower torque ripple, improving the PMSG efficiency for the engine optimum fuel consumption; also it is able supply unbalanced loads with the constant-amplitude and constant-frequency output voltages.

The Fig. 14 depicts the gen-set system efficiency when is operating at variable speed (blue line) and at constant speed (green line).

Fig. 11 – Gen-set torque and speed curves (blue line: reference).

Fig. 12 – PMSG voltages and currents.

Fig. 13 – Output voltages (phase-neutral) and unbalanced currents.

Fig. 14 – Gen-set global efficiency comparison (blue line: variable speed; green line: constant speed).

Analysing the Fig. 14, when the power load change from 20kW to 10kW at 2s, in variable speed operating mode, the gen-set efficiency remains constant at 30%, while in the constant speed operating mode, the gen-set efficiency drops to 27%.

V. CONCLUSIONS

In this paper an adjustable speed generating system model with diesel engine, PMSG and the back-to-back power electronic converter is presented.

The power control strategy for variable speed gen-set is proposed to optimize the engine fuel consumption. The decrease of fuel consumption is clear at low power loads when the gen-set operates at variable speed.

This control strategy is based on the voltage DC-bus dynamics which is sensitive to output load variations. When the voltage DC-bus changes, due the load changes, the PI controller establishes the mechanical power value that diesel engine should provide. At the same time this procedure activates the speed and the torque control loops of the diesel engine and PMSG, respectively. These inner control loops are derived from the diesel engine performance map knowledge, allowing the optimal operation of this power generation system.

The numerical simulation results validates the back-to-back converter applicability to a stand-alone variable speed gen-set. With the active front-end rectifier, PMSG sinusoidal curves are obtained and the three-phase four-leg inverter performs a good solution to deal to unbalanced loads.

Future work includes simulation analysis under non-linear loads and experimental validation of this approach.

Other further development includes the experimental tests to obtain the fuel consumption curves and to define a more accurate transient model for a 20kVA, 400V-50Hz gen-set.

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